

A Correlational Study between the Number of children and Types of Mindsets

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Abstract:- Nowadays, some people prefer to have an only child because of the cost of raising children. From the hypothesis, the number of children influences the actions of children who behave in various situations. More precisely, developing, shaping; and affecting self-confidence, which is different and causes different mindsets in children, depends on the number of children. A person's mindset is a collection of ideas that influence how they perceive themselves, which can divide into two categories: a fixed mindset (where both abilities and skills are innate and cannot be improved) and a growth mindset (where both abilities and skills can be developed via education, experience, and effort). This study aims to identify the correlation between the number of children and Dweck's Mindset Theory.

Therefore a 12-item online questionnaire with 12 closed-ended questions was created using a 5-Likert scale to test the hypothesis that children with siblings lead higher self-confidence than the only child. A total of 100 voluntary responses were received. The analysis supported the theoretical framework that there was a moderate positive correlation between the child with siblings and a growth mindset ($r=4.23$). On the contrary, The correlation between a single child and a growth mindset ($r=4.13$) was lower than the previous one. Moreover, this research also showed a moderate positive correlation between single children and a fixed mindset ($r=2.58$), which was higher than the correlation between the child with siblings and a fixed mindset ($r=2.22$). From this research, There is a responsibility that children with siblings influence the development of individual growth mindsets. Therefore parents and teachers need to enhance their children's skills and abilities through learning, experience, and effort to develop a growth mindset and build self-confidence in children. In conclusion, a child with siblings is more likely to construct a growth mindset promoting self-confidence.

Keywords:- Growth mindset, fixed mindset, a child with siblings, single child, self-confident, sibling relationship, sociability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, more people consider and take notice of improvement in their children since it is vital in the 21st century. As a result, many perceive that they should focus on the mindset of their children because mindset influences children's behavior and improvement. Dweck's mindset theory describes mindsets between people who believe in their effort to acquire new knowledge flexibly and others who believe in their ability. However, some researchers believe that the number of children affects the way that children behave, (Jiao, Shulan, et al.) which may lead to their improvement. In other words, the only child and children with siblings behave differently regarding self-confidence, development, and shaping themselves. Therefore the hypothesis in this research illustrates both theoretically and statistically. The topic focuses on students (15-19 years old) learning performance and how they react to challenging tasks, which refer to their mindset.

Moreover, the behavior of the only child and children with siblings would influence different mindsets. After the theoretical arguing and definitive statistics, a correlational assessment is performed to provide solid evidence of some points of view of these two frameworks regarding others. This research can raise awareness regarding how parents and mothers cope with their children to support them to grow their mindsets in the long term.

A. Mindsets

A mental attitude that determines how they think, perceives their abilities, and solves problems under various circumstances is described to be a mindset. The mentality hypothesis investigates individuals' attitudes to the points and explains why some people get disheartened by failure or withdraw when confronted with hurdles (Dweck, 1986). Nevertheless, Individuals have different behaviors and actions, such as people who believed their intelligence could be developed and confidence (growth mindset) outperformed those who believed their intelligence was fixed (fixed mindset) (Carol Dweck, 2015). However, the way that parents or teachers praise their child affects the mindsets of that person. It is noticeable that parents who have multiple children nurture their children differ from a single child's parents, thus, it shows that the praise from parents influences students to have different types of mindsets.

On the one hand, Growth mindset, people perceive that their general intellectual ability can improve, can foster academic achievement (Aronson, Fried, & Good, 2002; Blackwell, Trzesniewski, & Dweck, 2007), and care less about looking smart, they concern about how to develop themselves and put a lot of effort on it (Carol Dweck, 2016). In addition, they believe that hard work could improve their skills and they have more self-confidence, they would not be afraid due to failure.

On the other hand, a person with a fixed mindset does not like challenges because they are afraid of looking bad or scared to lose. As a result, they perceive that their skills and abilities could not be improved. Hence, a fixed mindset person thinks more negatively than a person with a Growth Mindset.

B. The different between single and multiple child

Different studies about self-confidence in children by learners have been carried out. (Goel et al., 2012) said that the number of children leads to more confidence in a child. The number of children is different in each Family, which divides into only children and children with a sibling.

An only child is a person having no siblings, either biological or adopted. (Arora et al., 2021) They tend to receive full attention, which studies say that their parents have higher expectations of them and more amenities to offer.

Newman, 2001) Thus the only child is self-centered and achievement-oriented and displays a desirable personality. Furthermore, sibling relationships are the starting point for children's socialization. Siblings are usually children's first playmates, enemies, and role models. (Linda L. Dunlap, 2004) Consistent with the theory, the Family is the first and the most critical structure in human civilization in which social lifestyles, mutual understanding, and compatibility are learned. (M. Alidosti et al., 2016) However, children with siblings—they make friends as quickly as their peers with siblings. (Heidi Riggio, 1999) To sum up, children with a sibling might have more self-confidence than only children because siblings have many delightful, warmhearted moments. A sibling can act as emotional support and communication partner. Also, positive sibling relationships in adolescence contributed to a sense of emotional and mindset support. (Santrock John W., 2016)

II. THEORETIC FRAMEWORK

In accordance with previous information passages, we hypothesized that children with siblings positively correlated with a growth mindset. A single child could lead to a positive correlation with a Fixed mindset.

As specified by another research, a Child with siblings has more self-confidence than a single child (Goel et al., 2012). On top of that, another research stated that a growth mindset promotes self-confidence (Tan Owee et al., 2015). Therefore, we conjecture that a child with siblings is more likely to develop a growth mindset than a single child.

III. METHODS

Dwellers in Thailand received the self-administered survey form that was distributed. A total of 100 survey respondents from various ages (between 15 to 19) comprised 50 from the single child group, and the rest was from the child with siblings in the current conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic. Our findings focus on collecting data from survey respondents, which was an uncomplicated and proper method. In the survey form, The respondents were advised about the finding's purpose and informed consent in the survey form. Our research was completed with 12 questionnaire statements, all of which were closed-ended 5-point Likert-type scales ranging from strongly agree (scale 5) to disagree (scale 1) strongly. The statements were divided into growth mindset (GM) and Fixed mindset (FM). Table 1 displays the statements and the relevant categories. The sequence of these assertions was rearranged to avoid the demand for characteristics being produced. The questionnaire prompted respondents to choose just one of five scales that best represented the level of their assent. The online questionnaire was concluded after the total number of each category, single child and child with siblings, reached 50. The data were examined through statistics, which employed mean scores and standard deviation values to illustrate how the statistics were dispersed. The averages of the statements in the very same group were then used to analyze the correlation between the categories. The simplification of correlation coefficients was based on Mukaka (2012), in which symbols + and - in front of numbers represent positive and negative correlation, respectively. Furthermore, numbers between 0.0 and 0.3, between 0.3 and 0.5, between 0.5 and 0.7, between 0.7 and 0.9, and above 0.9 present negligible, weak, moderate, strong, and robust correlation, respectively. Nonetheless, if suitable, these findings focus on a predictable trend of connected factors, even if the figures are considered to be a negligible correlation for discussion goals, without considering generalizing the research.

No.	Statement	Category identified
1	I usually avoid leadership roles whenever I do the task .	FM
2	I prefer not to failed.	FM
3	I believe that truly smart people do not need to try hard.	FM
4	I believe that skills cannot be created.	FM
5	I have no interest about learn new skills.	FM
6	I am often resentful or envious when I hear about other people’s success.	FM
7	Even if what I do will not succeed, I will keep trying to find a way to do it.	GM
8	I always get along with others.	GM
9	I am invariably prepare to learn new things.	GM
10	When I confront challenging tasks, I am sure I can accomplish them.	GM
11	I perceive that my ability could be developed.	GM
12	I usually turn failure into a lesson.	GM

Table 1: Types of mindset questionnaire items

IV. RESULTS

According to Table 2. The statistics illustrated that the mean score of the Growth mindset was 4.18, and the Fixed mindset was 2.40. In other words, These findings are based on data collected from survey respondents, which the majority had a growth mindset.

	Category	Mean
1	Growth mindset	4.18
2	Fixed mindset	2.40

Table 2: Average figures results based on types of mindset questionnaires (N=100)

V. DISCUSSION

It is noticeable among the 100 respondents that the numbers for growth mindset were much more significant than fixed mindset nearly times, which these figures can reflect that the higher the level of growth mindset, the better self-confidence. More precisely, self-confidence promotes people to accomplish achievements despite obstacles and is more likely to prioritize solving tricky challenges(Kosterlitz, 2015) more significantly than a fixed mindset would (Dweck, 2009)

Category	GM	FM
SC	4.13	2.58
CS	4.23	2.22

Table 3: Correlation coefficients based on types of mindset questionnaires (N=100)

According to Table 3, the degree of relation illustrates a moderate positive correlation between growth mindset and children with siblings. Vice versa, a weak positive correlation is shown in the correlation between the fixed mindset and single child. Consequently, this result encourages the theoretical framework (described in section 2). From the analyzed perspective, empirical evidence of a growth mindset and children having siblings should be created.

If people with this mindset face challenges with similar problems, they will be able to handle solutions better than the former because they have developed skills in dealing with them. Therefore, this could imply people can be more enabled to learn how to improve and overcome these challenges through their experiences because of their former mistakes. This results in developing a growth mindset in which their belief-ability and skills are malleable, and they accept feedback for improvement

(Bandura, 1982a; Dweck, 2006), leading to further developing self-confidence (Tan Owee et al., 2015) .

Consequently, recommended to both parents and siblings who can reassure their children. Furthermore, this must be emphasized on emotional support , and communication partners.(Feldman.,2006) They need a substitute for those who learn social skills, and compassion and conflict resolution make them more confident.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, statistical approaches investigated the association between the number of children (single child and child with siblings) and mindset types (growth and fixed mindset) that promoted self-confidence (Tan Owee et al., 2015). Based on a statistical approach and 100 respondents, the study's findings provide evidence to establish the link between the number of children and mindset types. There was a moderate correlation between a growth mindset and a child with siblings ($r = 4.23$) even though the correlations between a fixed mindset and a child with siblings were insignificant ($r = 2.22$), and vice versa, the correlations between a fixed mindset and a single child ($r = 2.58$). However, there is a negligible correlation between a growth mindset and a single child ($r = 4.13$).

This research can recommend that parents and teachers are more likely to develop a growth mindset in a child with siblings. More precisely, if parents educate their children to have a growth mindset, this might develop self-confidence.

First and foremost, a fixed mindset that prioritizes intelligence-based compensation above effort-based praise would have adverse effects. For instance, children's learning abilities may show less growth due to avoiding barriers that cause stagnation, preventing barriers that cause stagnation and due to their conviction that their abilities, skills, and talents are natural and cannot be developed. Lastly, a child with self-confidence may be motivated to learn new things, not be afraid to make mistakes, and always aspire to do better. The youngsters are therefore more likely to achieve their goals in terms of performance.

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